

The Effects of Inorganic Salts on the Rate of Mutarotation of Glucose

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The mutarotation of glucose is the change in rotation of either the α or β -form of (for example) $R(+)_D$ glucose after dissolution in water, from initial specific optical rotations of $+112^\circ$ for the α -form and $+19^\circ$ for the β -form, to an equilibrium specific rotation of $+52.7^\circ$, over a period of approximately three hours (depending upon environmental conditions). It is well-known that pH changes alter the rate of mutarotation of glucose. However, it has been found that the addition of certain metal salts (e.g., $FeCl_3$ and $NiCl_2$) to a solution of the α or β forms of the sugar also affects the mutarotation rate of glucose, while the addition of one enantiomer of an optically active complex compound has been found to have no effect on its mutarotation rate. A mechanism for the metal ion catalysis of the mutarotation of glucose is proposed.

THE crystalline form of glucose is quite stable, but it has been found that, in water, interconversion of the α - and β -anomers takes place. This interconversion can be followed by the change in optical rotation with time of a freshly prepared solution of either isomer. When crystals of α - $R(+)_D$ glucose are dissolved in water, the specific optical rotation drops from an initial value of $+112^\circ$ to $+52.7^\circ$ in three hours at room temperature. When crystals of β - $R(+)_D$ glucose obtained¹ from crystallizations above $98^\circ C$, are dissolved in water, the specific rotation increases from an initial value of $+19^\circ$ to $+52.7^\circ$. The term "mutarotation" is ascribed to this change in rotation of the different forms of glucose to an equilibrium value.

Mutarotation takes place under very mild conditions of acidity and temperature, and changes in acidity and temperature greatly influence the rate of interconversion of the α and β forms. For example, a 10° rise in temperature increases the rate of mutarotation by 2.5 times.² Within the pH range of 3.0 to 7.0, the rate of mutarotation is at a minimum, but outside this range, the rate increases rapidly. At $20^\circ C$, the mutarotation rate is slowest at $pH=4.61$.³

In this paper, the effects of the addition of one enantiomer of an optically active complex compound and metal salts on the rate of mutarotation of glucose are reported.

Experimental

R -glucose was obtained from Baker and Adamson and was of reagent grade quality. The $[Co(en)_3]Cl_3$ complex (en = ethylenediamine) was synthesized and resolved by the method of Douglas⁴. The metal salts were

obtained in reagent grade quality from several commercial suppliers. All sugar solutions were freshly prepared before each experiment. Other solutions were freshly prepared as needed. The optical purity of all optically active reagents was checked polarimetrically.

Absorption spectra were taken on a Cary Model 14 UV-VIS Spectrophotometer. Optical rotatory dispersion (ORD) measurements were made on a Cary-60 Recording Spectropolarimeter with a circular dichroism attachment. ORD and uv-vis studies were made in quartz absorption cells of various path lengths, each being fitted with a ground-glass stopper. All volumetric glassware was Class A, and pH measurements were done with a Leeds and Northrup Co. pH Indicator.

Results and Discussion

When freshly prepared solutions of glucose are prepared, mutarotation occurs in about three hours at room temperature. However, in the presence of metal salts, the rate of mutarotation increases.

Glucose with $FeCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$.

The effect of iron(III) on the rate of mutarotation is rather pronounced (Fig. 1). In the presence of iron(III), the process of mutarotation is complete in about 30 minutes. Since it is known that mutarotation is sensitive to changes in hydrogen ion concentration, and that iron(III) chloride solutions are acidic, pH values of the solutions involved were determined and

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Figure 1. The Effects of Metal Ions on the Mutarotation Rate of *R*-(+)*D* Glucose in H_2O . [Glucose] = 0.023 *M*; [Fe(III)] = 0.02 *M*; [Ni(II)] = 0.02 *M*. Path Length = 2 cm.

are given below.

Solution	pH
0.02 <i>M</i> $FeCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$	1.6
0.023 <i>M</i> <i>R</i> -Glucose	5.9
0.02 <i>M</i> $FeCl_3$ + 0.023 <i>M</i> <i>R</i> -Glucose	1.4

The pH of the iron-sugar solution is below the range where mutarotation is at a minimum³. Therefore, mutarotation studies of glucose at pH = 1.6 were made to determine whether the catalysis was due to the pH of the solution or to the presence of $FeCl_3$ or both. Fig. 2 shows the mutarotation rate of glucose, glucose with $FeCl_3$, and glucose at pH = 1.6. It can be concluded that iron(III) does influence the rate of mutarotation of glucose, but that the effect of the pH of the salt solution is also important. In addition, the concentration dependence of iron(III) on the rate of mutarotation was determined. When the concentration of iron(III) is doubled, the rate of mutarotation remains the same, which implies that the mutarotation of sugar is independent of the concentration of iron(III).

Figure 2. Mutarotation Rates of *R*-(+)*D* Glucose in Water Solution (a) in the Presence of Iron(III) (b), and at pH = 1.5 (glucose + HCl) (c). Solvent is H_2O . Path Length = 2 cm. [Glucose] = 0.023 *M*; [Fe(III)] = 0.02 *M*.

In order to determine if any complexation of the sugar with iron occurs, the ORD spectra of freshly prepared solutions of sugar alone, sugar with iron(III), mutarotated sugar alone, and mutarotated sugar with iron(III), as well as the absorption spectra of the iron-sugar mixtures were all recorded. The spectra of the mixtures were superimposable on the spectra of the component parts, and it can therefore be concluded that no complexation occurs between the sugar and the iron(III) salt in the concentration ranges utilized in this work.

Glucose with $NiCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$. The effects of nickel(II) on the mutarotation rate of glucose were not so striking as those of iron(III). However, $NiCl_2$ proved to be a fairly effective catalyst, causing mutarotation to be completed in about 1.5 hours (Fig. 1) at room temperature. Hydrogen ion concentration was not a factor, since the pH of both the sugar and nickel-sugar solutions was the same. The ORD spectra of the nickel-sugar mixture is the same as that of the sugar alone, while the absorption spectra of both solutions give one peak with the same intensity at 393 nm., indicating that no complexation occurs between nickel(II) and the sugar in the concentrations used in this experiment.

Glucose with other metal salts. The catalytic behavior of iron(III) and nickel(II) on the mutarotation of glucose suggests that a search for another metal ion that might exhibit a similar catalytic behavior should be undertaken. Iron(II) showed a much weaker effect than iron(III), and manganese(II), which is isoelectronic ($3d^6$) with iron(III), showed little activity as a catalyst for mutarotation. Chromium(III) showed little effect as a catalyst, indicating that metal ion charge alone is not an important factor. Copper(II) and ruthenium(III) were also not effective catalysts. None of the systems studied showed evidence of complexation of sugar to metal. Some of these results are summarized in Fig. 3 and in Table 1.

Figure 3. The Effects of Copper(II) and Chromium(III) on the Mutarotation Rate of *R*-Glucose in H_2O . [Glucose] = 0.023 *M*; [Cu(II)] = [Cr(III)] = 0.02 *M*. Path Length = 2 cm.

TABLE I—THE EFFECTS OF METAL IONS ON THE MUTAROTATION RATE OF R(+)-D-GLUCOSE

Metal	Effect of Mutarotation Rate
Iron(III)	++++
Nickel(II)	+++
Chromium(III)	++
Copper(II)	+
Ruthenium(III)	+
Manganese(II)	+
Iron(II)	+

Glucose with optically active complexes. In a similar manner, the catalytic activity of the optically active complexes Λ_3 , (+)-D [Co(en)₃]³⁺ and Δ_3 , (-)-D [Co(en)₃]³⁺ on the mutarotation rate of R-glucose were investigated. These studies showed that the mutarotation rate of glucose is not affected by the presence of these complexes.

Determination of the rate constants. The mutarotation of α -anomer to the β -anomer at any time, t, is given by

$$-\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k_1[\alpha] - k_2[\beta] \quad (2)$$

where k_1 = forward rate constant ($\alpha \rightarrow \beta$)

k_2 = reverse rate constant ($\beta \rightarrow \alpha$)

$[\alpha]$ = concentration of α -form at any time

$[\beta]$ = concentration of β -form at any time

The integrated form of equation (2) may be expressed using observed optical rotation as

$$k_1 + k_2 = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{[\alpha_0 - \alpha_\infty]}{[\alpha_t - \alpha_\infty]} \quad (3)$$

where α_0 = observed rotation at t=0

α_t = observed rotation at any time, t

α_∞ = observed equilibrium rotation

The sum $k_1 + k_2$ is known as the mutarotation coefficient and has the same value regardless of which isomer is being observed².

A plot of $\log(\alpha_t - \alpha_\infty)$ vs. time is shown in Fig. 4. Since $(\alpha_0 - \alpha_\infty)$ is a constant, the mutarotation coefficients for the systems studied can be calculated directly from the plot. The values for these coefficients are found in Table 2.

TABLE 2—MUTAROTATION COEFFICIENTS ($k_1 + k_2$) FOR R-GLUCOSE AND METAL ION R-GLUCOSE SYSTEMS

System	$k_1 + k_2$ (min. ⁻¹)
R-Glucose	1.2×10^{-2}
R-Glucose + Nickel(II)	1.6×10^{-2}
R-Glucose + Iron(II)	4.9×10^{-2}

Figure 4. The Mutarotation Rates of ——— R-Glucose ; - - - R-Glucose + Ni(II) ; - · - · - R-Glucose + Fe(II). Slope = $k_1 + k_2$.

Mechanism of the catalysis of mutarotation of glucose by metal ions: Both hydrogen and hydroxyl ions are capable of catalyzing mutarotation reactions. According to Lowry⁵, both acids and bases simultaneously catalyze the mutarotation of sugar. In addition, he⁶ proposed that mutarotation is a ternary reaction in which both acids and bases are catalysts at the same time. According to this theory, the acid catalyst, HA, protonates the ring oxygen at the same time the base catalyst, B, deprotonates the C₁ hydroxyl group, yielding the sugar aldehyde⁷.

It is herewith proposed that the mechanism of catalysis by metal ions follows a similar path. According to Pearson's⁸ Hard and Soft Acid-Base Theory, iron(II), manganese(II) and chromium(II) would be considered hard acids, and should catalyze the mutarotation of glucose as well as the proton. All the other metal ions (Table 2) are either soft acids or borderline cases. Ether groups (the ring oxygen in glucose) are considered to be hard bases. In every metal ion-sugar system studied, the metal ion served as a more effective catalyst than the proton when compared to solutions of the same pH containing sugar alone. Therefore, it is proposed that the metal ion attacks the ring oxygen while an OH⁻ deprotonates the C₁ hydroxyl, resulting in ring opening, which leads to interconversion of the ring isomers (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Proposed Mechanism of Metal Ion Catalysis of the Mutarotation of Glucose.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to express their appreciation to the U. S. National Science Foundation and the Romanian Council of Science and Technology for research grants which contributed significantly to the progress of this investigation.

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